

Amides of *Piper amalago* var. *nigrinodum*

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An endemic Jamaican variety of *Piper amalago* has afforded six amides. Four are known compounds, and two (1 and 2) are new. Two-dimensional NMR spectroscopy has been used to assign the structures of the new amides and to assign completely the ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of the known compounds. All six amides have been tested for insecticidal activity against *Aedes aegyptii* larvae; some activity is observed and related to molecular features. But none of the compounds show activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

Metabolites of the Piperaceae have excited both chemical and biological interest because they have been found to have insecticidal and antifungal activities. *Piper amalago* var. *nigrinodum* C. DC (Piperaceae) is an endemic Jamaican variety¹ of *P. amalago*, which occurs throughout the tropical Americas and the West Indies. Its phytochemistry has been described^{2,3}; isolates consist mainly of amides of various aliphatic and aromatic acids, with pyrrolidides and isobutylamides predominating.

In our investigation, dried milled leaves and stems were separately extracted with hexane followed by acetone. Roots were extracted with acetone only. The extracts were subjected to column chromatography over silica gel, and selected fractions were chromatographed further to provide the two new amides, 1 and 2, and four known compounds, 3-6. Structures and spectra were assigned with the aid of COSY, HMQC, and HMBC two-dimensional NMR spectra.

Compound 1, 7-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2E,4E-heptadienoic acid pyrrolidide, given the trivial name nigrinodine, was isolated as a pale yellow oil from the root extract (0.0069% of dried root). The formula C₁₈H₂₁NO₃ was assigned by HREIMS, and IR bands at 1655, 1600, and 1499 cm⁻¹ indicated an α,β -unsaturated amidic carbonyl and an aromatic ring. From the ¹H NMR data (Table 1), this ring was seen to be 1',3',4'-trisubstituted with a methylenedioxy group linking positions 3' and 4'. Corroboration was found in the strong 3-bond cross peaks in the aromatic region of the HMBC spectrum. A correlation between the *ortho*-coupled aromatic proton (δ_{H} 6.72, d, 8.0 Hz) and the quaternary aromatic carbon at δ_{C} 135.43 established this as the C-1' position. This carbon also showed

cross peaks to two mutually coupled methylene protons (H₂-7 and H₂-6). The C-6 methylene protons were also coupled to the terminal (δ) proton (H-5, δ_{H} 6.38, dt, 16.0, 7.0 Hz)

*Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri, chemist and friend, on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Table 1. NMR data for nigrinodine (1)*

Position	δ_C (n_H)	δ_H (J , Hz)	HMBC
1	165.56 (0)	–	5.80
2	118.10 (1)	5.80 (d, 16.0)	–
3	141.61 (1)	7.40 (dd, 16.0, 10.8)	5.97, 5.80
4	127.87 (1)	5.97 (dd, 16.0, 10.8)	5.80, 2.43
5	140.47 (1)	6.38 (dt, 16.0, 7.0)	7.40, 2.67, 2.43
6	34.94 (2)	2.43 (dt, 7.3, 7.0)	2.67
7	35.08 (2)	2.67 (t, 7.3)	6.68, 6.62, 6.38, 2.43
1'	135.43 (0)	–	6.72, 2.43
2'	108.80 (1)	6.68 (d, 1.5)	6.62, 2.67
3'	145.62 (0)	–	6.72, 6.68
4'	147.50 (0)	–	6.72, 6.68
5'	108.12 (1)	6.72 (d, 8.0)	6.62
6'	121.12 (1)	6.62 (dd, 8.0, 1.5)	6.68, 2.67
7'	100.74 (2)	5.90 (s)	–
1''	46.90 (2)	3.53 (m)	3.45, 1.92, 1.84
2''	26.63 (2)	1.92 (m)	3.53, 1.92, 1.84
3''	24.37 (2)	1.84 (m)	3.53, 3.45, 1.92
4''	45.51 (2)	3.45 (m)	3.53, 1.92, 1.84

*NMR data in Tables 1–6 are provided in the following manner.

Column 2 shows chemical shift (δ_C) of assigned carbon and number of attached protons (n_H).

Column 3 shows chemical shift (δ_H) of attached proton(s), and apparent multiplicity and coupling constants. Connectivities were established by HMQC.

Column 4 shows δ_H for protons showing two- or three-bond correlations with the assigned carbon (HMBC). Only observed cross-peaks are reported.

of the $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ doubly unsaturated amide; *trans*-stereochemistry was assigned to both carbon-carbon double bonds on the basis of the observed 1H - 1H couplings. The pyrrolidide ^{13}C and H signals were at their characteristic positions, but it is worth noting that the methylene groups (1'', 2'') *syn* to the carbonyl groups were slightly deshielded relative to their *anti* counterparts (4'', 3''). The non-equivalence arises because of slow rotation about the amide bond. (A similar non-equivalence may be observed in the other pyrrolidides described below). A *cis*-isomer of nigrinodine has been reported recently as a constituent of *P. hispidum*⁴.

Compound 2, 2'-methoxy-4',5'-methylenedioxy-*trans*-cinnamoylisobutylamide, was obtained as a white solid (0.0013% of dried root), m.p. 150–152°, from the root extract. The formula $C_{15}H_{19}NO_4$ was assigned by HREIMS, and the IR spectrum showed amide and aromatic peaks (3298, 1663, 1612 cm^{-1}). In the 1H NMR spectrum (Table 2), a six-proton doublet at δ 0.95, a one-proton multiplet at δ 1.84, and a two-proton triplet at δ 3.22 (coupled to the

Table 2. NMR data for 2'-methoxy-4,5-methylenedioxy-*trans*-cinnamoylisobutylamide (2)

Position	δ_C (n_H)	δ_H (J , Hz)
1	166.62 (0)	–
2	119.01 (1)	6.28 (d, 15.0)
3	135.65 (1)	7.84 (d, 15.0)
1'	141.58 (0)	–
2'	154.61 (0)	–
3'	94.79 (1)	6.52 (s)
4'	141.58 (0)	–
5'	149.78 (0)	–
6'	106.72 (1)	6.95 (s)
7'	101.52 (2)	5.96 (s)
8'	56.51 (3)	3.85 (s)
1''	47.05 (2)	3.22 (t, 6.0)
2''	28.71 (1)	1.84 (m)
3'', 4''	20.18 (2×3)	0.95 (d, 6.0)
NH	–	5.3–5.55

broadened N–H signal at δ 5.34) were assigned to the isobutyl group. Signals in the low-field region consisted of a two-proton singlet at δ 5.96, characteristic of a methylenedioxy group, a pair of *trans*-coupled doublets (J 15.0 Hz) at δ 6.28 and 7.84, assigned to the α and β cinnamoyl protons, and two one-proton singlets at δ 6.52 and 6.95, assigned to the *para*-related protons of a 1,2,4,5-tetrasubstituted aromatic ring. The proton data and the ^{13}C chemical shifts observed for the cinnamoyl component of 2 are very similar to those reported previously³ for the corresponding moiety in 2'-methoxy-4',5'-methylenedioxy-*trans*-cinnamoylpyrrolidide (3), which was also isolated in this study (Table 3). The NMR data for 2 differ from those reported for the isomeric compound, 3',4'-methylenedioxy-5'-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamoylisobutylamide (5'-methoxy-fagaramide), previously been found in *P. amalago*² but not isolated in this study.

In addition to 3, the known compounds trichostachine (4)⁵, piperidine (5)⁶, and guineensine (6)⁷ were identified from spectroscopic data, and by comparison of these and other physical data with published values. The fully assigned NMR data of 4, 5 and 6 are provided in Tables 4, 5 and 6.

All six amides were tested for activity against 4th instar larvae of *Aedes aegyptii* L. (Culicidae) at a concentration of 100 ppm. Table 7 shows the results and the percentage mortality at varying time intervals for compounds that were active at 100 ppm. Active preparations were diluted and further assayed to determine minimum lethal concentrations (Table 8). The insecticidal properties of isobutylamides from

Table 3. NMR data for 2'-methoxy-4',5'-methylenedioxy-*trans*-cinnamoylpyrrolidide (3)

Position	δ_C (n_H)	δ_H (J, Hz)
1	165.47 (0)	–
2	116.99 (1)	6.60 (d, 16.1)
3	136.62 (1)	7.93 (d, 16.1)
1'	141.47 (0)	–
2'	154.67 (0)	–
3'	94.82 (1)	6.53 (s)
4'	141.47 (0)	–
5'	149.76 (0)	–
6'	106.68 (1)	6.97 (s)
7'	101.54 (2)	5.95 (s)
8'	56.54 (3)	3.83 (s)
1''	46.55 (2)	3.56 (m)
2''	26.19 (2)	1.92 (m)
3''	24.44 (2)	1.92 (m)
4''	45.99 (2)	3.56 (m)

Piperaceae have been established^{8,9} and the activity of pipericide (5) and guineensine (6) has been described¹⁰.

The isobutylamide of 2'-methoxy-4',5'-methylenedioxy-*trans*-cinnamic acid (2) was slightly active, while the corresponding pyrrolidide 3 was inactive. This may be attributed to the greater lipophilicity of 2, which enables faster absorption by the insect⁹. Of the pyrrolidides, only nigrinodine (1) showed mosquitocidal activity. This could be attributed to the longer chain-length of 1 relative to 3 and 4. Nigrino-

Table 4. NMR data for trichostachine (4)

Position	δ_C (n_H)	δ_H (J, Hz)	HMBC
1	164.94 (0)	–	7.40, 6.26, 3.56
2	121.35 (1)	6.26 (d, 14.7)	6.75
3	141.79 (1)	7.40 (dd, 14.7, 10.2)	6.81, 6.75
4	125.18 (1)	6.75 (dd, 14.7, 10.2)	7.40, 6.81, 6.26
5	138.69 (1)	6.81 (d, 14.7)	7.40, 6.99, 6.91
1'	130.98 (0)	–	6.81, 6.78, 6.75
2'	105.68 (1)	6.99 (d, 1.6)	6.91, 6.81
3'	148.20 (0)	–	6.99, 6.78, 5.97
4'	148.16 (0)	–	6.99, 6.91, 6.78, 5.97
5'	108.47 (1)	6.78 (d, 8.0)	6.91
6'	122.55 (1)	6.91 (dd, 8.0, 1.6)	6.99, 6.81, 6.78
7'	101.26 (2)	5.96 (s)	–
1''	46.50 (2)	3.56 (m)	3.56, 2.00, 1.90
2''	26.15 (2)	2.00 (m)	3.56, 1.90
3''	24.38 (2)	1.90 (m)	3.56, 2.00
4''	45.94 (2)	3.56 (m)	3.56, 2.00, 1.90

Table 5. NMR data for pipericide (5)

Position	δ_C (n_H)	δ_H (J, Hz)	HMBC
1	166.28 (0)	–	7.19, 5.76, 3.19
2	121.90 (1)	5.76 (d, 14.8)	6.14
3	141.16 (1)	7.19 (dd, 14.8, 10.2)	–
4	128.41 (1)	6.14 (dd, 14.8, 10.2)	5.76
5	142.71 (1)	6.10 (m)	7.19, 2.17
6	32.78 (2)	2.14–2.20 (m)	6.14
7	28.95 (2)	1.44 (m)	2.17
8	28.33 (2)	1.44 (m)	6.04, 2.17
9	32.67 (2)	2.14–2.20 (m)	6.29, 6.04
10	128.95 (1)	6.04 (m)	–
11	129.58 (1)	6.29 (d, 14.8)	6.89, 6.74, 6.04
1'	132.38 (0)	–	6.74, 6.29, 6.04
2'	105.41 (1)	6.74 (m)	6.78, 6.29
3'	147.93 (0)	–	6.74
4'	146.60 (0)	–	6.89, 6.78, 6.74
5'	108.21 (1)	6.89 (d, 8.0)	–
6'	120.22 (1)	6.78 (m)	6.89, 6.29
7'	100.91 (2)	5.96 (s)	–
1''	46.94 (2)	3.19 (dd, 6.0, 6.8)	1.80, 0.94
2''	28.65 (1)	1.80 (m)	3.19, 0.94
3'', 4''	20.13 (2×3)	0.94 (d, 6.0)	3.19, 1.80, 0.94
NH	–	5.47 (br)	–

dine (1) was less active than pipericide (5) or guineensine (6) (Table 8), possibly because its shorter chain-length results in lower lipophilicity and because it is a pyrrolidide rather than an isobutylamide. Guineensine (6), the isobutylamide with the longest chain, was the most active.

Compounds 1–6 were also tested for activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and were found to be inactive at concentrations of 12.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ ¹¹

Experimental

Plant material was collected at Ramgoat Cave, Trelawny, Jamaica, and identified as *Piper amalago* var. *nigrinodum*. A voucher specimen ([#]33803) is preserved in the UWI Herbarium at Mona.

Dried leaves (1.1 kg) were milled and cold-percolated successively with hexane and acetone, providing two gums (29 and 40 g, respectively). An aliquot (8 g) of the gum from the hexane extraction was subjected to two stages of column chromatography (silica gel with acetone-hexane gradient eluant), and afforded trichostachine (4; 8 mg), m.p. 142–144° (lit.⁵ 142–143°); NMR data (Table 4). In a similar way, an aliquot (15 g) of the gum from the acetone extraction afforded 2-methoxy-4',5'-methylenedioxy-*trans*-

Table 6. NMR data for guineensine (6)

Position	δ_C (n_H)	δ_H (J, Hz)	HMBC
1	166.29 (0)	—	7.19, 5.74, 5.50, 3.16
2	121.72 (1)	5.75 (d, 15.5)	—
3	141.22 (1)	7.19 (dd, 15.5, 9.8)	6.12
4	128.22 (1)	6.12 (dd, 15.5, 9.8)	7.19, 5.74
5	143.02 (1)	6.10 (m)	7.19, 2.15, 1.42
6	32.89 (2)	2.15 (m)	6.12, 1.45
7	29.34 (2)	1.45 (m)	—
8	28.99 (2)	1.33 (m)	2.15
9	28.63 (2)	1.33 (m)	—
10	28.72 (2)	1.42 (m)	—
11	32.84 (2)	2.15 (m)	6.28, 6.05
12	129.31 (1)	6.05 (m)	—
13	129.58 (1)	6.28 (d, 15.5)	—
1'	132.42 (0)	—	6.05
2'	105.35 (1)	6.75 (m)	6.28
3'	147.86 (0)	—	6.91, 6.75
4'	146.47 (0)	—	6.91, 6.76, 6.75
5'	108.21 (1)	6.91 (d, 8.0)	—
6'	120.15 (1)	6.76 (m)	6.91, 6.28
7'	100.87 (2)	5.96 (s)	—
1''	46.91 (2)	3.16 (dd, 7.0, 6.0)	5.50, 1.81, 0.94
2''	28.65 (1)	1.81 (m)	3.16, 0.94
3'', 4''	20.13 (2×3)	0.94 (d, 6.0)	3.16, 1.81, 0.94
NH	—	5.50 (br)	—

cinnamoylpyrrolidide (3; 12 mg), m.p. 177–179° (lit.³ 178–179°); NMR data (Table 3).

Dried roots (960 g) were ground and percolated with cold acetone to provide a gum (20 g). An aliquot (10 g) was subjected to column chromatography (silica gel with acetone-hexane eluant). The residue (850 mg) obtained from elution with 20% acetone was rechromatographed with the same gradient system. The fraction eluted with 15% acetone af-

Table 7. Mosquitocidal activity of compounds 1–6 at 100 ppm

Compd. no.	% Mortality at time (h)					
	2	4	6	8	12	24
1	100	100	100	100	100	100
2	0	0	0	0	0	20
3	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	100	100	100	100	100	100
6	100	100	100	100	100	100
DMSO	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 8. Assay of mosquitocidally active compounds

Compd. no.	% Mortality at conc. shown after 24 h		
	3 ppm	1.5 ppm	0.75 ppm
1	63	44	16
5	70	57	20
6	100	92	78

forded guineensine (6; 21 mg), m.p. 110–111° (lit.⁷ 113–115°); NMR data (Table 6). The mother liquor provided a residue (240 mg) that was rechromatographed in an EtOAc-hexane system and then in an acetone-hexane system, affording nigrinodine (1; 33 mg) as an oil: v_{max} 2375, 2330, 1655, 1600, 1499 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 268 (4.39), 307 (4.26), 345 nm (4.10); HREIMS 299.1535 (calcd. for $C_{18}H_{21}NO_3$ 299.1521); EIMS 299 (40), 164 (24), 150 (38), 135 (100), 70 (8); NMR data (Table 1).

The root extract fraction eluted with 20% acetone afforded piperide (5; 7 mg), m.p. 120–122° (lit.⁶ 120°); NMR data (Table 5). The fraction eluted with 30% acetone yielded a gum (800 mg) that was subjected to repeated chromatography (acetone-hexane) to afford 2'-methoxy-4',5'-methylenedioxy-*trans*-cinnamoylisobutylamide (2; 6 mg) as white plates from hexane-toluene, m.p. 150–152°; v_{max} 3298, 1663, 1612 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 227 (4.67), 274 (4.56), 336 (4.26); HREIMS 277.1314 (calcd. for $C_{15}H_{19}NO_4$ 277.1314); EIMS 277 (38), 246 (100), 205 (69), 190 (72), 175 (16), 147 (8); NMR data (Table 2).

The root extract fraction eluted with 40% acetone afforded compound 3 (10 mg), identical with the material from the leaf extract (above).

One- and two-dimensional NMR spectra were obtained on a Varian Unity-500 spectrometer equipped with an inverse detection 5 mm probe. Two-dimensional spectra were obtained using standard Varian software. All spectra were obtained with samples in $CDCl_3$ and referenced to internal $(CH_3)_4Si$.

Mosquitocidal assay: Fourth instar (2–3 days old) larvae of *Aedes aegypti* L. (Culicidae) were reared in the Bioactive Natural Products Laboratory from eggs obtained from the Department of Entomology, Michigan State University. Larvae (10–15) were placed in 980 μ l of degassed distilled water, and test samples dissolved in 20 μ l of DMSO were added to produce a concentration of 100 ppm; control larvae received 20 μ l of DMSO. Initial concentrations were then diluted serially to determine the minimum lethal concentration. Tests were carried out at room temperature, and the number of dead larvae were recorded at intervals of 2, 4, 8, 12 and 24 h.

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11. Compounds were tested by the Tuberculosis Antimicrobial Acquisition and Coordinating Facility (TAACF), supported by the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID) and operated by the Southern Research Institute, Birmingham, Alabama, U.S.A.

